

Optical and upconversion properties of Pr³⁺-doped Ba₃La(PO₄)₃ and Ba_{2.5}La_{1.5}(PO₄)_{2.5}(SiO₄)_{0.5}.

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Abstract

UVC radiation is renowned for its potent antiseptic properties, making it highly effective for water and surface decontamination. Thus, developing new UVC-generating materials is essential. In the present work, new UVC-emitting Pr³⁺-doped Ba₃La(PO₄)₃ and Ba_{2.5}La_{1.5}(PO₄)_{2.5}(SiO₄)_{0.5} phosphors were synthesized using the Pechini method, and their optical and upconversion properties were investigated. Both compounds crystallize in a cubic eulytite-type structure. The emission spectra reveal a significantly higher intensity of the ¹D₂ → ³H₄ (575-645 nm) transition compared to the ³P₀ → ³H₄ (465-505 nm) transition. Emission decay curves indicate non-mono-exponential behavior due to variations in the local crystal field environment, with lifetime shortening observed at higher Pr³⁺ concentrations due to concentration quenching effects. Under ultraviolet excitation, both compounds demonstrate efficient 5d-4f emission, while under 444 nm laser excitation, upconversion photoluminescence in the UVC range is observed via a two-photon process, primarily governed by excited-state absorption (ESA). The highest UVC upconversion emission is achieved with 1.5% Pr³⁺ doping, with Ba_{2.5}La_{1.5}(PO₄)_{2.5}(SiO₄)_{0.5} exhibiting ~30% higher upconversion intensity than Ba₃La(PO₄)₃ due to enhanced local disorder and favorable crystal field effects. These materials outperform YPO₄:Pr³⁺ phosphate in upconversion emission, highlighting their potential for use in UVC-emitting devices.

Introduction

Luminescent materials are integral to many modern devices, including optical sources, displays, lasers, data storage systems, dosimeters, high-speed luggage scanners, and CT scanners. These materials are typically inorganic or organic compounds consisting of a host lattice doped with an activator, which is often a transition or rare earth ion. The interest in host matrices doped with rare earth elements that exhibit luminescence began in the 1930s and has grown steadily due to the development of new applications and evolving industrial requirements.

One of the remarkable properties of rare earth doped luminescent materials is their ability to exhibit upconversion emission. There is strong demand for generating artificial UV light for various applications, such as surface decontamination, photopolymerization, solar hydrogen

production, and the treatment of skin diseases, including cancer [1, 2, 3]. Current methods of UV generation are costly, inefficient, and environmentally harmful. Therefore, an innovative approach to generating UV radiation is to convert visible radiation into ultraviolet [4]. Pr³⁺-doped compounds, with their lowest 4f5d states lying below the 4f²(¹S₀) level, show great potential in this regard. In these materials, the ¹D₂, ³P₁ and ¹I₆ levels of the 4f² configuration can act as intermediate states for upconversion [5, 6]. Depending on the band gap of the compounds, upconversion emission can occur in the UVA (320-400 nm), UVB (280-320 nm), and UVC (200-280 nm) ranges [7, 8]. The least-studied and most unique materials are those that exhibit visible-to-UVC upconversion [9]. UVC radiation rapidly neutralizes most types of pathogens by being absorbed by the RNA or DNA molecules within them. For instance, UVC emission from Li₂SrSiO₄:Pr³⁺ under laser excitation, with a maximum emission power density of 0.25 mW/cm², inactivated all bacteria within 10 minutes [10].

By now, various Pr³⁺-doped inorganic compounds have been reported to exhibit visible-to-UVC upconversion. Upconversion has been reported in LiYF₄:Pr³⁺, BaYF₅:Pr³⁺, Lu₇O₆F₉:Pr³⁺, Y₂Si₂O₇:Pr³⁺, Sr₂SiO₄:Pr³⁺, YPO₄:Pr³⁺, Ca₉Y(PO₄)₇:Pr³⁺ and others [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17]. Particularly good candidates for UVC upconversion are phosphates and silicates due to their simple synthesis methods at low temperatures, high chemical and moisture stability, relatively large band gaps, strong luminescence, and transparency in the ultraviolet region. Our attention was drawn to the double orthophosphate Ba₃La(PO₄)₃ with a cubic eulytite-type structure (S.G. *I* $\bar{4}$ 3*d*) [18]. While luminescent properties of Ce³⁺-doped, Sm³⁺-doped, and Eu³⁺/Tb³⁺-codoped Ba₃La(PO₄)₃ phosphors have been previously reported [19, 20, 21, 22], the luminescent properties of Pr³⁺-doped Ba₃La(PO₄)₃ have not been studied until now.

Given the often relatively low efficiency of upconversion (around 5%), one method to enhance this property is through partial substitution of cations or anionic groups. In this respect, an anionic group such as orthophosphate (PO₄³⁻) can be easily partially replaced by the silicate anion (SiO₄⁴⁻) without altering the original crystal structure. Both anionic groups are tetrahedra, though with some differences. Forming a 3D network, SiO₄⁴⁻ tetrahedra can share all four oxygens with neighboring anion groups, whereas only three oxygen atoms in PO₄³⁻ group can be shared. This difference arises because silicon has a charge of +4, while phosphorus has a nominal charge of +5. As a result, one oxygen atom in the PO₄³⁻ group shares its two unpaired electrons with phosphorus to form a terminal double bond. Consequently, the charges of the PO₄ and SiO₄ anionic groups are different, being 3- and 4-, respectively.

Thus, we also decided to investigate the effect of replacing the PO₄³⁻ group with SiO₄⁴⁻ in Ba₃La(PO₄)₃, with the expectation of enhancing upconversion performance. To maintain charge balance when replacing the orthophosphate anion with silicate, the ratio of Ba and La atoms in the structure of Ba₃La(PO₄)₃ must be adjusted. The resulting compound, which retains a structure similar to that of Ba₃La(PO₄)₃, is Ba_{2.5}La_{1.5}(PO₄)_{2.5}(SiO₄)_{0.5}. By retaining orthophosphate groups, we preserve biocompatibility, while the introduction of silicate groups alters the band gap, increases compound stability, and enables the production of bulk glass samples.

In summary, this study investigates the luminescence properties, upconversion properties, and lifetimes of the phosphors $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ (BPO) and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ (BSiO) in detail for the first time.

Experimental

Sample preparation

A series of $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5-x}\text{Pr}_x(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}$ ($x=0.00, 0.10, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1.00, 1.50, 2.00$) phosphors was synthesized by the sol-gel method using La_2O_3 (99.99%), Pr_2O_3 (99.9%), $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (pure p.a.), $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ (99.999%), citric acid (pure p.a.), HNO_3 (65%, pure p.a.), ethylene glycol (pure p.a.), tetraethoxysilane (99.9%) and freshly prepared distilled water.

In the case of $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Pr}_x(\text{PO}_4)_3$, the starting materials La_2O_3 and Pr_2O_3 were weighed in stoichiometric proportions and dissolved in 65% nitric acid. A stoichiometric amount of $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, previously dissolved in distilled water, was then added to the mixture and stirred for 10 minutes. A water solution of citric acid (prepared from powder weighed with a 200% excess per cations) was mixed with the aqueous metal nitrates and further stirred for 20 minutes. An aqueous solution of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (prepared from powder $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ taken with a 130% excess) was added, followed by another 20 minutes of stirring. Ethylene glycol (taken with a 200% excess per cations) was then added to enhance the reaction. The resulting mixture was stirred for 2 hours and evaporated to form a viscous gel. The gel was dried and annealed at 500°C for 5 hours. The resulting dark-grey powder was thoroughly ground in an agate mortar and annealed again at 1150°C for 8 hours. In the case of $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5-x}\text{Pr}_x(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}$, before adding the ethylene glycol, a stoichiometric amount of tetraethoxysilane was added, and the resulting mixture was stirred for 30 minutes.

To compare the upconversion intensity, $\text{YPO}_4:1\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ was used as a reference sample. It was prepared by the sol-gel method using Y_2O_3 (99.99%) and Pr_2O_3 (99.9%) as starting components. The rest of the sample preparation procedure, except for the adding $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, was identical to that of the $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ series.

Measurements

The phase purity of the $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:x\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:x\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ series was verified by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD). The PXRD measurements were performed using an X'Pert PRO θ - θ powder diffractometer (Malvern Panalytical Ltd., Malvern, UK) with parafocusing Bragg-Brentano geometry, employing an Emyrean Cu LFF (long fine-focus) HR X-ray tube with a Ni β -filter (thickness 0.02 mm; $K_\beta=1.392250 \text{ \AA}$) and K_α radiation ($K_{\alpha 1}=1.540598 \text{ \AA}$, $K_{\alpha 2}=1.544426 \text{ \AA}$, K_α ratio 0.5, $K_{\alpha\text{av}}=1.541874 \text{ \AA}$). The operating voltage of the X-ray source was 40 kV, and the tube current was 30 mA. The diffraction patterns were collected using an ultrafast PIXcel1D detector from 5 - 90° (2θ) with a step size of 0.026° (2θ) and a counting time of 133.37 s per step. Data were analyzed using the Match 3 software.

The excitation and emission spectra in the visible range, along with the photoluminescence decay profiles, were acquired using an FLS1000 photoluminescence spectrometer (Edinburgh instruments Ltd., Livingston, UK) equipped with a 450 W ozone-free xenon arc lamp (230-2600 nm), a xenon microsecond flashlamp, and a PMT-980 detector (Hamamatsu Photonics K.K., Hamamatsu, Japan). To measure the emission and excitation spectra of the crystallites at 77 K, the spectrophotometer was coupled with a Linkam THMS 600 Heating/Freezing Stage (Linkam Scientific Instruments Ltd., Salfords, UK).

The upconversion luminescence spectra were obtained using a McPherson Vacuum UV Spectrophotometer (McPherson Inc., Chelmsford, USA) under 444 nm continuous wave laser excitation. The crystallites were placed in a special holder with a lithium fluoride window. All samples were measured under identical conditions using a Hamamatsu R7154P photomultiplier tube (Hamamatsu Photonics K.K., Hamamatsu, Japan), in conjunction with a UG5 color glass filter (Eksma Optics, Vilnius, Lithuania). Lifetime upconversion measurements were recorded upon pulse excitation of the samples with the second harmonic of a Ti:sapphire laser, pumped by the second harmonic of an Nd:YAG laser, both from LOTIS TII Ltd. (Minsk, Belarus). A Pellin-Broca prism was used to separate the sum-frequency beam from the fundamental line of the Ti:sapphire laser and the pump laser components.

Results and discussion

Figure 1. Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of the $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:x\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ (a) and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:x\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ (b) series with the relevant ICSD reference patterns.

Figure 1 presents the powder X-ray diffraction results for a series of $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:x\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:x\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ ($x=0.00, 0.10, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1.00, 1.50, 2.00$), which were synthesized using the sol-gel method. Pure phases were obtained in all compositions, with PXRD patterns closely matching the ICSD standards. The replacement of PO_4^{3-} by SiO_4^{4-} and the variation in Pr^{3+} doping concentration appear to have minimal impact on the lattice unit cell, as the diffraction patterns remained consistent. The unit cells of all the samples were indexed in cubic symmetry, described by the space group $I\bar{4}3d$ (220). The structure of $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ adopts the

eulytite-type structure ($\text{Bi}_4(\text{SiO}_4)_3$) (Figure 2). This structure consists of a three-dimensional network of isolated $[\text{PO}_4]^{3-}$ tetrahedra and edge-sharing $[(\text{Ba/La})\text{O}_6]^{9-}$ octahedra [Jacques Barbier]. Barium and lanthanum share the same crystallographic site, occupying the 16c Wyckoff position, with site occupancy factors (SOFs) of 0.75 for Ba and 0.25 for La, respectively [Jacques Barbier]. Substituting the larger Ba^{2+} ion (ionic radius $r_{\text{Ba}^{2+}}=1.35 \text{ \AA}$, CN=6 [1]) with the smaller and differently charged La^{3+} ion (ionic radius $r_{\text{La}^{3+}}=1.03 \text{ \AA}$, CN=6 [1]) introduces significant structural disorder. This is evidenced by the presence of two distinct oxygen species, O1 and O2, with SOFs of 0.3542 and 0.6458, respectively.

An even greater degree of disorder is introduced when phosphate groups are partially replaced by silicate groups $(\text{SiO}_4)^{4-}$. Due to the different charges of $(\text{SiO}_4)^{4-}$ and $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$, additional La^{3+} ions must be incorporated to maintain charge neutrality, necessitating a reduction in Ba^{2+} content per unit cell. Furthermore, the larger size of the Si^{4+} ion compared to P^{5+} (0.26 \AA vs. 0.17 \AA for CN=4 [1]) contributes to increased structural disorder, which in turn affects the emission spectra and decay dynamics.

Figure 2. Structure of $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3$. Phosphorus and oxygen are connected by bonds in $[\text{PO}_4]^{3-}$, showing the possible clockwise or anticlockwise rotations of the $[\text{PO}_4]^{3-}$ tetrahedron around its 2-fold axis.

Figure 3. Excitation and emission spectra of 3P_0 and 1D_2 for $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:1\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ (a, b) and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:1\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ (c, d).

Figures 3a and 3c depict the excitation spectra in the visible range for $\text{BPO}:1\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{BSiO}:1\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$, monitored between 400 and 500 nm at emission wavelengths of 602.5 and 603.75 nm, respectively. The spectra for both compounds are almost identical and consist of three peaks at ~ 442 , 470 and 481 nm, corresponding to the ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_J$ ($J=2, 1, 0$) transitions, respectively [23]. The most intense transition, at 442 nm (3P_2), was used as the excitation wavelength for recording the emission spectra. The emission spectra of the same compounds, observed in the 465-750 nm spectral range, are also presented in Figures 3a and 3c (green lines). Both spectra are also almost identical and demonstrate typical emission bands for Pr^{3+} -doped phosphates, where the ${}^1D_2 \rightarrow {}^3H_4$ (575-645 nm) transition has much higher intensity in comparison with the ${}^3P_0 \rightarrow {}^3H_4$ (465-505 nm) transition [24]. The proximity of the 3P_J energy levels favors radiationless energy transitions from the 3P_2 level to the 3P_1 and 3P_0 levels, from which transitions to lower levels occur with the emission of light. The energy differences between the 3P_0 and 1D_2 levels, as derived from the excitation spectra, are less than 4000 cm^{-1} for both compounds, while the highest phonon energy in phosphate matrices is 1200 cm^{-1} [25]. In this case, the energy difference is less than five

times the phonon energy, which means that, according to the energy bandgap law, the probability of multiphonon relaxation is substantial [26]. Therefore, the 1D_2 level can be populated by multiphonon relaxation from the 3P_0 level, followed by the predominance of emission from the 1D_2 level (~ 600 nm). To demonstrate that the most intense luminescence corresponds to the $^1D_2 \rightarrow ^3H_4$ transition, studies were carried out on the luminescence of the 1D_2 level under 579 nm excitation (Fig. 3b and 3d, red lines). The emission peaks observed in the range 575-645 nm in Fig. 3a and 3c (green lines) are consistent with the peaks found in the 590-645 nm range in Fig. 3b and 3d. Figures 3b and 3d (orange lines) display excitation spectra monitored at 625 nm, corresponding to transitions originating from the 3H_4 ground level to the higher energy level 1D_2 of Pr^{3+} .

Figure 4. Decay curves of the 3P_0 and 1D_2 emission, acquired from $Ba_3La(PO_4)_3:x\%Pr^{3+}$ (a,b) and $Ba_{2.5}La_{1.5}(PO_4)_{2.5}(SiO_4)_{0.5}:x\%Pr^{3+}$ (c,d) crystallites with different Pr^{3+} concentrations.

Figure 5. Emission decay times as a function of Pr^{3+} concentration for the $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ samples (represented by blue circles and pink squares, respectively) for: a) the $^3\text{P}_0$ level, and b) the $^1\text{D}_2$ level.

Figure 4 shows lifetime decay profiles of the $^3\text{P}_0$ and $^1\text{D}_2$ emissions recorded from the $\text{BPO}:x\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{BSiO}:x\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ crystallites with different Pr^{3+} concentrations. The decay profiles follow non-mono-exponential decay models, indicating variations in the local environment of the Pr^{3+} ion [27]. This can be explained by differences in crystal field strength, which cause slight variations in the transition probabilities of Pr^{3+} energy levels, resulting in multiple decay rates within the same group of Pr^{3+} ions. The average lifetimes were estimated using equation [28]:

$$\tau = \frac{\int tI(t)dt}{\int I(t)dt} \quad (1)$$

The decay constants are summarized in Figure 5. The decay time becomes faster with increasing Pr^{3+} concentration due to concentration quenching [29, 30, 31]. The calculated decay times for $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:x\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ are slightly longer in comparison with the pure phosphates.

The La:Ba ratio differs between the samples, being 1:3 for BPO and 3:5 for BSiO. This implies that Pr^{3+} ions in the BSiO lattice have 1.8 times more available sites to occupy, being randomly distributed and more dispersed, which reduces the probability of ion pair formation. Thus, the likelihood of Pr^{3+} pair formation is higher in the BPO sample.

The partial substitution of the larger, but lighter Ba^{2+} ion (density of solids = 3510 kg/m^3) with the smaller, but heavier La^{3+} ion (6146 kg/m^3), along with the replacement of phosphorus (1823 kg/m^3) by silicon (2330 kg/m^3), leads to a reduction in the lattice vibrational energy. This, in turn, suppresses nonradiative multiphonon relaxation processes and results in increased lifetimes of the $^3\text{P}_0$ level in BSiO samples (see Fig. 5a).

It is well known that the 1D_2 level is efficiently depopulated via spin-allowed cross-relaxation (CR) processes such as $^1D_2 + ^3H_6 \rightarrow ^1G_4 + ^3P_1$ [32, 33]. This CR mechanism is more effective in BPO due to the higher concentration of Pr^{3+} pairs. Consequently, the 1D_2 emission lifetime decreases more rapidly in BPO than in BSiO (see Fig. 5b). However, the efficient CR also leads to partial repopulation of the 3P_0 level in BPO, resulting in a slower reduction in its lifetime with increasing Pr^{3+} concentration compared to BSiO (see Fig. 5a).

Figure 6. Upconversion emission spectra of $Ba_3La(PO_4)_3:1\%Pr^{3+}$, $Ba_{2.5}La_{1.5}(PO_4)_{2.5}(SiO_4)_{0.5}:1\%Pr^{3+}$ and $YPO_4:1\%Pr^{3+}$ (reference), acquired under identical measurement conditions.

When Pr^{3+} ions in the $BPO:1\%Pr^{3+}$ and $BSiO:1\%Pr^{3+}$ hosts were excited at 444 nm, the upconversion emission signals from 230 to 315 nm were recorded (see Figure 6). These peaks can be assigned to transitions from the 4f5d band to the 3H_J and 3F_J levels [34]. Both phosphate and phosphosilicate exhibit significantly higher upconversion luminescence intensity compared to the reference $YPO_4:1\%Pr^{3+}$. Furthermore, as depicted in Figure 6, 80% of the observed upconversion spectrum for both compounds falls within the UVC range, with 20% in the UVB range. A study of the dependence of integral upconversion luminescence intensity in the UV range on activator concentration for both phosphate and phosphosilicate showed that, with increasing Pr^{3+} concentration, the upconversion emission intensity increases, reaching a maximum at 1.5% (Figure 7a). A further increase in Pr^{3+} content leads to concentration quenching of the upconversion emission [35].

Let us now consider the evolution of upconversion emission intensity as a function of dopant concentration (Fig. 7a). When these data are normalized and plotted on a double-logarithmic scale (Fig. 7b), it is evident that the emission intensity in BSiO varies linearly with Pr^{3+} concentration. In contrast, for the BPO sample, the slope of the intensity curve is 1.4, indicating that Pr^{3+} ion pairs are likely forming in this material. To show the variation area between

linear and quadratic dependence, the dependencies $I = x^2$ (orange line) and $I = x$ (purple line) are shown, where I is the Intensity of the UC emission and x is the Pr^{3+} concentration.

Figure 7. (a) Integrated upconversion emission intensity for $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$. (b) Normalized upconversion emission intensity as a function of dopant concentration for the BSiO and BPO samples. To show the variation area between linear and quadratic dependence, the trends $y = x^2$ (orange line) and $y = x$ (purple line) are shown. Inset: upconversion luminescence intensity versus laser pump power for $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:1\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:1\%\text{Pr}^{3+}$.

To determine the number of photons involved in upconversion, the dependence of upconversion intensity on laser pump power was studied [36]. The results are presented in the inset of Figure 7b on a double logarithmic scale. The fitted slopes for BPO:1%Pr³⁺ and BSiO:1%Pr³⁺ are 2.1 and 2.19, respectively, indicating the involvement of two photons in the excitation process of upconversion luminescence. Thus, it can be assumed that either excited state absorption (ESA) or energy transfer upconversion (ETU) is present [37]. To unambiguously determine which process is responsible for upconversion, the lifetime of upconversion was studied (Fig. 8). It is known that the lifetime of the ETU process is half the lifetime of the emission from the ³P₀ level, which, in our case, should be more than 1 μs [38]. In the case of the ESA mechanism, the lifetime corresponds to the emission from the 5d4f level and lies in the range of tens of nanoseconds [39]. The upconversion (UC) emission decay curves exhibit a biphasic character. The initial component is characterized by a short decay constant on the order of a few nanoseconds (Fig. 8b), while the second component displays a significantly longer decay constant, extending to several hundred nanoseconds. These two decay components correspond to distinct UC excitation mechanisms under pulsed excitation conditions. The dominant process is ESA, whereas the weaker contribution arises from ETU. Notably, in the BPO sample, the ETU mechanism appears to be more pronounced than in BSiO. It is also important to emphasize that the dominant UC mechanism can differ

depending on the excitation regime; pulsed and continuous-wave (CW) excitation often activate different UC pathways.

Figure 8. (a) Decay of upconversion emission under 443.4 nm pulsed excitation for $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:0.75\% \text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:0.75\% \text{Pr}^{3+}$. (b) Decay time constant of the upconversion emission.

It should be noted that the upconversion emission intensity of $\text{BSiO}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ is approximately 30% higher than that of BPO. It can be assumed that, in the case of the phosphate-silicate, the 5d4f level is lower compared to pure phosphate, allowing for more effective energy transfer. To confirm this, excitation spectra under synchrotron irradiation were studied. Figure 9a shows the normalized excitation spectra recorded at 8 K for emission at 602.3 nm. The excitation spectra exhibit broad bands centered in the ultraviolet range, attributed to the 4f-5d spin-allowed absorption transition of Pr^{3+} [40]. The substitution of smaller PO_4^{3-} tetrahedra with larger SiO_4^{4-} tetrahedra, along with the simultaneous replacement of Ba^{2+} with La^{3+} ($r_{\text{Ba}^{2+}}=1.35 \text{ \AA}$ and $r_{\text{La}^{3+}}=1.03 \text{ \AA}$, CN=6) for charge balance, results in a reduction of the $\text{Pr}^{3+}\text{-O}$ distance [41]. This reduction modifies the crystal field strength around Pr^{3+} , increasing it and thus resulting in the observed red shift in $\text{BSiO}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$. Figure 9b displays broad emission from 220 to 350 nm when excited by 200 nm, which is attributed to the 5d-4f transition. It is essential to highlight that, with the introduction of SiO_4^{4-} tetrahedra into the structure, broadening of the bands in both the excitation and emission spectra is observed. This can be attributed to disorder in the local environment of Pr^{3+} (Fig 9 a,b) [42]. Thus, the spectral changes highlight the sensitivity of 4f-5d transitions to both cationic and anionic substitutions in the crystal lattice.

To summarize, a study of the excitation spectra at the synchrotron has demonstrated that the 4f5d level for silicate-phosphate compounds is lower than that for pure phosphate, resulting in more intense upconversion. Another possible explanation could be the participation of the $^1\text{D}_2$ level in the upconversion mechanism as an intermediate level, as reported in [6, 43]. Since the sum of the $^1\text{D}_2$ and $^3\text{P}_1$ levels for both compounds, marked with a dashed line in Fig. 9a, is slightly below the 4f5d level, only the $^3\text{P}_1$ level participates in the ESA mechanism as an intermediate level.

Figure 9. Excitation (a) and emission spectra of $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:0.5\% \text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:0.5\% \text{Pr}^{3+}$ using synchrotron radiation.

Conclusions

$\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ crystallites doped with different concentration of Pr^{3+} were synthesized using the Pechini method, and their optical and upconversion properties have been studied. Both compounds crystallize in cubic symmetry adopting the eulytite-type structure. Their excitation and emission spectra are similar. The emission spectra of $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ demonstrate typical emission bands for Pr^{3+} -doped phosphates, with the $^1\text{D}_2 \rightarrow ^3\text{H}_4$ (575-645 nm) transition exhibiting much higher intensity in comparison with the $^3\text{P}_0 \rightarrow ^3\text{H}_4$ (465-505 nm) transition. Emission decay curves show non-mono-exponential decay profiles, indicating variations in the crystal field environment of Pr^{3+} ions. The decay times shorten with increasing Pr^{3+} concentrations, suggesting concentration quenching effects. Crystallites of $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ activated by Pr^{3+} demonstrate effective ultraviolet 5d-4f emission upon ultraviolet excitation.

$\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ exhibit upconversion photoluminescence in the UVC range under 444 nm laser excitation. The upconversion emission of Pr^{3+} occurs via a two-photon process. The upconversion decay time study determined that excited-state absorption (ESA) is the primary mechanism responsible for upconversion, with lifetimes in the range of 16–21 ns. The highest upconversion emission within the UVC range was observed in the 1.5% Pr^{3+} -doped samples. The introduction of $[\text{SiO}_4]^{4-}$ tetrahedra and $\text{Ba}^{2+}/\text{La}^{3+}$ substitutions alters the local crystal environment, leading to enhanced upconversion intensity and broadening of spectral bands due to increased disorder. Thus, $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ demonstrates a ~30% higher upconversion emission intensity than $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:\text{Pr}^{3+}$. Crystallites of $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ exhibit a manifold increase in upconversion emission compared to $\text{YPO}_4:\text{Pr}^{3+}$, suggesting their potential applications in industry, phototherapy and sterilization.

In summary, compositional modifications of $\text{Ba}_3\text{La}(\text{PO}_4)_3:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ towards $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ significantly impact the luminescent properties, especially upconversion emission. The superior performance of $\text{Ba}_{2.5}\text{La}_{1.5}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.5}(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.5}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ in upconversion is attributed to a more favorable crystal field environment and the fact that the 5d4f level is lower compared to pure phosphate, allowing for more effective energy transfer. These findings highlight the potential of silicate-phosphate compounds in advanced photonic applications, such as UVC-emitting devices, due to their tunable optical properties and high upconversion efficiency.

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